

SUPPLEMENT 2. Chinese scientific names of the new family, new genera, new species and new combinations proposed in this study.

Scientific Names	
Latin	Chinese
Atramentodiscaceae	砚碟菌科
<i>Atramentodiscus</i>	砚碟菌属
<i>Atramentodiscus nanshaensis</i>	砚碟菌 (南沙砚碟菌)
<i>Agaricus cantonotraminus</i>	轨道蘑菇
<i>Hymenagaricus conghuaensis</i>	从化层蘑菇
<i>Leucocoprinus phantasmaticus</i>	缢魂白鬼伞
<i>Amanita huangpuensis</i>	黄埔鹅膏
<i>Clitopilus zoysiae</i>	结缕草斜盖伞
<i>Calvatia scandens</i>	攀岩秃马勃
<i>Marasmiellomyces entolomoides</i>	粉褶蕈状微皮小菇
<i>Floriboletus</i>	花城牛肝菌属
<i>Floriboletus tianheensis</i>	花城牛肝菌 (天河花城牛肝菌)
<i>Floriboletus puellaris</i>	美丽花城牛肝菌
<i>Hygrophoropsis pleurotoides</i>	侧耳状拟蜡伞
<i>Satyrium rugulosus</i>	细皱红鬼笔
<i>Daedalea atypa</i>	非典迷孔菌
<i>Kusaghiporia mesotalpae</i>	中柄巫孔菌
<i>Pycnoporus sinoruber</i>	中国红密孔菌
<i>Russula dulcicora</i>	甜心红菇